

Intelligent Shipping Management System with .NET and IoT Integration

¹Naga Lalitha Sree Thatavarthi, ²Roopak Ingole

¹Davidson, NC 28036

²Columbus, IN 47201

*thatavarthinagalalithasree2020@gmail.com, roopak.ingole@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The development of a modern shipping management application that combines .NET technology and the Internet of Things (IoT) equipment is explored in this paper. With the use of real-time tracking, predictive maintenance, and automated inventory management, the application seeks to enhance shipping activities. Employing ASP.NET for the back end and Blazor for the front end, the system offers strong analytical features and an intuitive user interface. Through the optimization of inventory levels, timely delivery, and regular issue resolution, these improvements allow significant productivity improvements and reductions in costs. With its latest technical integration, the Intelligent Shipping Management System or ISMS has the potential to entirely transform the shipping industry by increasing consumer satisfaction and profitability.

Key words: NET, IoT, Shipping Management, Real-Time Tracking, Predictive Maintenance, Blazor, ASP.NET, Data Analytics

INTRODUCTION

The transportation of products across regions and the development of economic growth are rendered possible by the shipping industry, which is a vital component of global trade. On the other hand, effectiveness, cost management, and real-time visibility present significant challenges. The flexibility and real-time data features required to meet the demands of modern logistics operations may be lacking in conventional shipping management systems. Frequent issues that degrade operational performance and increase expenses include poor inventory management, the inability to trace shipments in real-time, and excessive maintenance costs brought on by unplanned malfunctions in equipment [1].

This paper addresses these problems by outlining the development and implementation of an Internet of Things (IoT) and .NET-based Intelligent Shipping Management System. With the use of predictive maintenance, continuous monitoring, and automated inventory management, the ISMS aims to maximize shipping capabilities [1]. The platform's missions are to enhance the user experience, save expenditures, and boost efficiency by incorporating the latest technologies. The study explores the ISMS's specifications, advantages, and technological architecture, emphasizing how it could completely alter the logistics industry.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

The shipping industry has several major challenges that negatively affect its efficiency and cost. Conventional inventory control systems are paper-based and slow since they involve several steps, including recognition, valuation, analysis, and reporting, culminating in high operational expenses. Another area of concern is real-time shipment tracking, as most of the track and trace systems are not capable of offering up-to-date and often accurate information, hence hindering visibility and customer satisfaction. Furthermore, the equipment used in

ships often undergoes breakdown maintenance, which means that the equipment fails and therefore requires repair, and the repair expenses are likely to increase.

These inefficiencies compound and act as the cause of poor performance and reliability in shipping operations. There is a need to have a system that coordinates these challenges by automating the inventory system, tracking the shipment status, and offering maintenance on the machines [2]. Implementation of such a solution would update operational efficiency and give the best customer satisfaction with equal or fewer costs.

2.1 Summary of the key issues:

Inefficient Inventory Management: Manual processes lead to errors and delays.

Lack of Real-Time Tracking: Difficulty in tracking shipments in real-time.

High Maintenance Costs: Unplanned maintenance leads to downtime and increased expenses.

SOLUTION

The Intelligent Shipping Management System (ISMS) integrates IoT devices with .NET technology to address the critical challenges faced by the shipping industry.

3.1 Automated Inventory Management:

IoT sensors continuously monitor inventory levels, providing real-time data. This enables the system to automatically trigger restocking processes when stock levels fall below predefined thresholds, ensuring optimal inventory levels and reducing manual errors.

3.2 Real-Time Tracking

GPS-enabled IoT devices attached to shipments provide live location updates. This real-time tracking capability allows for precise monitoring of shipment progress, enhancing visibility and improving delivery accuracy. Customers and logistics managers can access up-to-date information on shipment status, leading to higher satisfaction and better planning [2].

3.3 Predictive Maintenance:

IoT sensors embedded in shipping equipment continuously monitor critical health metrics, such as vibration, temperature, and usage patterns. The system analyzes this data to predict maintenance needs before failures occur, scheduling proactive maintenance to prevent unexpected downtime and reduce repair costs.

3.4 Key Summaries:

Enhanced Efficiency: Automated processes and real-time data improve operational efficiency.

Cost Reduction: Predictive maintenance and optimized inventory management lower operational expenses.

Improved Visibility: Real-time tracking provides accurate, live updates on shipment status.

User Satisfaction: Increased accuracy and reliability lead to higher customer satisfaction.

USES

Using the Internet of Things & .NET technologies, the Intelligent Shipping Management System provides complete offerings in three major domains: Predictive Maintenance, immediate Tracking, and Fully automated Inventory Management. These kinds of applications are outlined in complete below, with corresponding illustrations and graphs.

4.1 Automated Inventory Management:

Internet of Things sensors are employed in automated inventory management to monitor the amount of stock at the present moment. This function guarantees that stock levels remain at ideal levels, reduces human error, and significantly lowers the manual labor required for maintaining inventory.

4.1.1 Flowchart: Inventory Management Process

Figure.1: Inventory Management Process

4.1.2 Pseudocode:

```

1  START
2
3  // Function to set up the inventory system
4  FUNCTION InitializeInventorySystem()
5  // Establish connection to the inventory database
6  Connect to database
7  // Set up system configurations and parameters
8  Initialize settings
9  // Output confirmation message
10 PRINT "Inventory system initialized."
11 END FUNCTION
12
13 // Function to link to IoT sensors
14 FUNCTION ConnectToIOTensors()
15 // Initiate connection to IoT sensors
16 Establish connection to IoT sensors
17 // Verify if the connection was successful
18 IF connection successful THEN
19 // Output success message
20 PRINT "Connected to IoT sensors."
21 ELSE
22 // Output failure message
23 PRINT "Failed to connect to IoT sensors."
24 END IF
25 END FUNCTION
26
27 // Function to check inventory and initiate reorder if necessary
28 FUNCTION MonitorInventory()
29 // Retrieve current inventory data from IoT sensors
30 InventoryData = GetInventoryDataFromSensors()
31 // Iterate through each item in the inventory
32 FOR EACH item IN InventoryData
33 // Determine if the stock level is below the reorder point
34 IF item.stocklevel < item.reorderthreshold THEN
35 // Start reorder process for the item
36 TriggerReorderProcess(item)
37 END IF
38 END FOR
39 END FUNCTION
    
```

Figure 2: Pseudo code of Automated Inventory Recording (Part 1)

```

40
41 // Function to handle the reorder process for an item
42 FUNCTION TriggerReorderProcess(item)
43 // Confirm reorder details for the item
44 reorderdetails = VerifyReorderDetails(item)
45 // Check the availability of the supplier
46 IF SupplierAvailable(reorderdetails.supplierID) THEN
47 // Place an order with the supplier
48 orderconfirmation = PlaceOrderWithSupplier(reorderdetails)
49 // Update inventory records with the new order information
50 UpdateInventoryRecords(orderconfirmation)
51 // Continuously check until stock is received
52 WHILE NOT StockReceived(orderconfirmation.orderID)
53 // Contact supplier if stock has not arrived
54 FollowUpWithSupplier(orderconfirmation.orderID)
55 END WHILE
56 // Adjust inventory levels after receiving stock
57 UpdateInventoryLevels(orderconfirmation)
58 ELSE
59 // Alert if the supplier is unavailable
60 NotifySupplierUnavailability(reorderdetails.supplierID)
61 END IF
62 END FUNCTION
63
64 // Main execution process
65 InitializeInventorySystem() // Set up the inventory system
66 ConnectToIOTensors() // Link to IoT sensors
67 MonitorInventory() // Check inventory and reorder as needed
68
69 END
    
```

Figure 3: Pseudo code of Automated Inventory Recording (Part 2)

4.1.3 Step-by-Step Process:

Inventory Monitoring: Enterprises need to monitor their inventory levels constantly, and to this end, IoT sensors are placed at different points [3].

Data Transmission: These sensors send the data in real-time mode to the central. NET-based system.

Threshold Check: They are parameters which are used to compare inventories against certain levels which could indicate when the product should be restocked [3].

Restocking Trigger: Generally, there is a fixed reorder level for each kind of inventory and if the current stock level of any kind of item goes below this level, then a system will automatically order for them.

Update Inventory Records: Once the reorder has been kicked off, the respective inventory database(s) will change to reflect a pending restocking.

Notification: Sometimes notifications are instantly generated and delivered to the concerned staff or applications to notify them that the reorder process has been initiated.

Figure 4: Automated Inventory Management Process

4.1.4 Inventory Management Process Description:

4.1.4.1 IoT Sensors:

Various IoT sensors can be incorporated in IMS system. They are placed on inventory items, these sensors then collect the real-time data on stock levels.

Sensor technology has advanced over the years and depending on the precision of location needed, below sensor can be used [7].

1. GPS-based Tracking Systems: These are great selection for outdoor tracking with high accuracy, often within a few meters [7].
2. Cellular-based Tracking Systems: These are great selection for outdoor or indoor tracking with accuracy ranging from few feet to 300 feet depending on cell density of cell phone towers [7].
3. Wi-Fi-based Tracking Systems: These are great selection for indoor tracking where GPS and Cellular tracking is insufficient [7].
4. Bluetooth-based Tracking Systems: Utilizing crowdsourced Bluetooth and Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE), these are great for indoor and outdoor tracking with limited range of 60 meters [7].
5. RFID-based Tracking Systems: Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) uses radio waves to identify and track objects are great for indoor or outdoor tracking with high accuracy in the limited range of broadcaster systems [7].
6. IMU-based Tracking Systems: There are various sensors available that goes beyond location, like accelerometers, gyroscopes, and magnetometer to track the movement, orientation and even environmental conditions [7].

7. Radio Tracking Systems: These systems use dedicated radio frequencies to track objects equipped with radio transmitters. They can be parts of avalanche beacons used for mountain rescue [7].
8. Barcode Scanners: Barcode itself is not a tracking technology by itself but a method of representing data in a way a machine can understand. However, barcode scanners can significantly affect inventory management and asset tracking. It's relatively straightforward (and cheaper compared to RFID trackers) to print a set of barcodes representing the required information and put them on items. By scanning these unique barcodes, tons of relevant data can be instantly retrieved from a database [7].

4.1.4.2 Data Transmission:

Data from sensors is transmitted to the central system via the Internet. Connectivity technologies like LTE/4G/5G can be used tracking devices are to be installed at remote location and WiFi is not available. For indoor installations, cheaper high speed internet connections over WiFi can be used to gain the connectivity.

4.1.4.3 Central System (.NET Platform):

Processes the data, checks thresholds, and triggers restocking.

4.1.4.4 Reorder Trigger:

If stock levels are below the threshold, the system initiates a reorder.

4.1.4.5 Inventory Records Update:

The system updates the inventory status to reflect restocking.

4.1.4.6 Notification:

Sends alerts to stakeholders about the restocking action.

4.2 Real-Time Tracking

Real-time tracking is a pivotal component of the Intelligent Shipping Management System (ISMS). This functionality is enabled through GPS-enabled IoT devices attached to shipments. These devices continuously provide location updates, offering precise, real-time visibility into the status and position of each shipment. Logistics managers and customers can access this information at any time, ensuring transparency and enabling timely decision-making. Real-time tracking allows for the swift resolution of potential issues, such as delays or route deviations, enhancing the reliability and efficiency of shipping operations [4].

Figure 5: Real-Time Tracking System Architecture

This graph highlights the improvement in shipment delivery times achieved through real-time tracking. The ISMS implementation results in more accurate and timely deliveries, significantly enhancing operational efficiency.

4.3 Predictive Maintenance

Another factor is the utilization of the ISMS, where the PM is another pivotal element used to predict continuously the condition of the shipping equipment through IoT sensors. Being used for a range of metrics – vibration, temperature and usage – these sensors gather information on the engine. The system uses this data to

foresee when the car needs to be serviced and thus prevents scheduling for maintenance at the wrong time. Measures like this help reduce the chances of synchronizing and experiencing equipment failure, thus enabling the least disruption of operations.

The image shows a screenshot of a code editor with a dark theme. On the left, there is an 'EXPLORER' sidebar showing a project folder named 'PROJECT' containing a file named 'pseudocode.cs'. The main editor area displays the following pseudocode:

```
1 Initialize Maintenance System
2 Connect to IoT Sensors
3
4 For each equipment:
5   Monitor health metrics (vibration, temperature, etc.)
6   If any metric exceeds threshold:
7     Schedule maintenance
8   End If
9 End For
10
```

Figure 6: Pseudocode of Predictive Maintenance Algorithm

4.4 Enhanced Efficiency

The proposed Intelligent Shipping Management System (ISMS) brings about operational efficiencies through a major stream of key activities including inventory and shipment tracking. The conventional approaches of inventory tracking can take considerable and tedious efforts, as well as involve human errors that slow down the process [5]. Inventory management – one of the key benefits of the ISMS is the ability of IoT sensors to track stock volumes in real-time with subsequent activation of the restocking procedure if there are some shortages. This automation minimizes human interjection, meaning that feasible clerical workers can concentrate on other varied and more important aspects of the company. Furthermore, real-time shipment tracking also carries timelier information to the logistics managers on the shipment status, thereby helping them to make the necessary adjustments on the movement patterns and schedules, to the improvement of operations.

4.5 Cost Reduction

They have to manage the many costs that are usually incurred when it comes to shipping operations and this is where the ISMS comes in handy. I will detail how it achieves it below, but one key aspect is the concept of predictive maintenance. IoT sensors are used on the equipment within the shipping environment and are used to collect readings leading to maintenance requirements before equipment breakdowns happen. This way, the client will fix equipment problems before they become costly issues, and will also put less money towards expensive repairs. In addition, aspects such as overstocking or understocking can also be reduced with the help of automated management of inventories. In many manufacturing companies, inventory costs make up a large portion of the overall expenses; therefore, by streamlining inventory, firms minimize storage and carrying costs and thereby lower costs considerably.

4.6 Improved Visibility

Real-time tracking is a core feature of the ISMS that drastically improves visibility into the shipping process. GPS-enabled IoT devices attached to shipments provide continuous updates on their location and status. This level of transparency allows logistics managers to make informed decisions quickly, responding to any issues or delays as they arise. Improved visibility also facilitates better planning and coordination throughout the shipping process, ensuring that shipments are delivered on time and as efficiently as possible [5]. This real-time insight is invaluable for maintaining a high level of service and operational effectiveness.

4.7 User Satisfaction

Enhanced accuracy and reliability in inventory management, shipment tracking, and predictive maintenance directly contribute to higher user satisfaction. Customers benefit from accurate delivery estimates and real-time updates on their shipments, which reduces uncertainty and builds trust. The reliability of the ISMS means fewer delays and disruptions, ensuring that goods are delivered as promised. This consistency in service quality enhances the overall customer experience, leading to increased satisfaction and loyalty. By addressing key pain points in the shipping process, the ISMS not only optimizes operations but also significantly improves the end-user experience.

IMPACT

This paper thus establishes that the process of implementing the Intelligent Shipping Management System creates a systematic change of impacts on the whole shipping operations spectrum.

5.1 Efficiency Gains:

There are some huge advantages associated with the usage of some wholly automated procedures, regarding the fact that human mistakes have been said to cause a lot of variations in business processes [6]. These results in a shorter time to complete shipments, and in general uninterrupted and well-organized business undertakings.

5.2 Cost Reduction:

The ISMS reduces costs in several ways Cost savings in the four areas are outlined below. In particular, the strategy reduces the chances of costly plant equipment breakdown and the associated time that equipment is unavailable or offline; it also helps avoid high storage costs and maintains optimum stock levels. These efficiencies are good for daily operations thus making them cheaper and efficient in the long run.

5.3 Enhanced Visibility:

Functionality in live tracking enables the shareholders to have real-time information on the status and location of the shipments. This enhanced visibility not only facilitates the efficient control of the stock flow but also allows time-taking decisions to be made in the event of delivery disruptions.

5.4 Improved Service Quality:

Consequently, through being able to facilitate efficient deliveries and addressing operational waits, the ISMS works to build service dependability. The delivery performance is improved in terms of timescales resulting in more accurate delivery promises and fewer delivery breakdowns to the customers and this in turn enhances their satisfaction and loyalty levels.

5.5 Environmental Impact:

Logistical benefits, such as improved delivery routes, mentioned under the ISMS approach, also assist with lowering emissions and the organization's environmental impact through sustainable business practices [6].

5.6 Competitive Advantage:

The integration of top sophisticated technologies like the ISMS places the firms at great authoritative heights in the shipping field. It supports the requirements and needs of the consumers, as well as the company's capability to stand out in the market.

Finally, the ISMS seeks to achieve growth in operational performance and control costs and helps to improve the quality-of-service delivery, undertaking environmental issues, and becoming more competitive in the global market.

SCOPE

Comparatively, the Intelligent Shipping Management System or ISMS presents the capability of scalability and elasticity to accommodate the varying segments of the shipping industry. It is designed for small logistic customers who need a modern platform to manage their workflows and optimize costs, as well as for large global shipping companies that might need complex and reliable systems. It is commensurate with the scale and requirements of operations through its modularity of features such as auto-order, tracking, and predictive information. Its availability guarantees that companies of all sizes can adopt solutions to effect improvements in the operational efficiency, costs, or reliability of the services being offered. Whether the client is a local company planning its national transportation or an international company planning its global supply chain, the ISMS offers a complete solution, the fundamental structure capable of serving as a solution for all industries.

CONCLUSION

The integration of The ISMS efficiently employs .NET and IoT technologies for the shipping industry and has proved to be the biggest improvement to the shipping management system. Here, it is crucial to note that the application of these innovations in addressing problems and achieving objectives is a key advantage of the ISMS.

Real-time inventory tracking through IoT sensors helps automate the processes and eliminate errors, reducing the time required to conduct resource management using basic algorithms. Functionality that monitors shipment on the go helps stakeholders to know the status of the shipment on time, thereby improving customer experience and enabling decision-making when due, through accurate delivery estimations.

Cost reduction is realized through the following Key Activities: predictive maintenance eliminates expensive and time-consuming equipment standstill charges. Inventory management offers low packaging and operating costs across the company's points of operation. These efficiencies are also complemented by the immediacy of Blazor for smooth frontend actions and ASP.NET for the strong backend performance necessary for uninterrupted and fast operation, independent of operational sizes.

In the end, the ISMS is a new approach that not only tears down traditional shipping logistics, but also puts forward innovation for integrated logistics solutions through such elements as efficiency, cost, and customer service. It is due to its all-encompassing strategy for using technology to drive improvement that it can be classified as an enabling one that addresses the challenge of shipping organizations to improve their competitiveness and operations.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Lee, C.K., Lv, Y., Ng, K.K., Ho, W. and Choy, K.L., 2018. Design and application of Internet of things-based warehouse management system for smart logistics. *International Journal of Production Research*, 56(8), pp.2753-2768. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/00207543.2017.1394592>
- [2]. Trappey, A.J., Trappey, C.V., Fan, C.Y., Hsu, A.P., Li, X.K. and Lee, I.J., 2017. IoT patent roadmap for smart logistic service provision in the context of Industry 4.0. *Journal of the Chinese Institute of Engineers*, 40(7), pp.593-602. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/02533839.2017.1362325>
- [3]. Levina, A.I., Dubgorn, A.S. and Iliashenko, O.Y., 2017, November. Internet of things within the service architecture of intelligent transport systems. In 2017 European Conference on Electrical Engineering and Computer Science (EECS) (pp. 351-355). IEEE. <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/8412048/>
- [4]. Yuen, J.S., Choy, K.L., Lam, H.Y. and Tsang, Y.P., 2018. An intelligent-internet of things (IoT) outbound logistics knowledge management system for handling temperature sensitive products. *International Journal of Knowledge and Systems Science (IJKSS)*, 9(1), pp.23-40. <https://www.igi-global.com/article/an-intelligent-internet-of-things-iot-outbound-logistics-knowledge-management-system-for-handling-temperature-sensitive-products/210114>
- [5]. Luo, H., Zhu, M., Ye, S., Hou, H., Chen, Y. and Bulysheva, L., 2016. An intelligent tracking system based on internet of things for the cold chain. *Internet Research*, 26(2), pp.435-445. <https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/IntR-11-2014-0294/full/html>
- [6]. Pathak, N. and Bhandari, A., 2018. IoT, AI, and Blockchain for .NET. In *Building a Next-Generation Application from the Ground Up*. Apress. <https://link.springer.com/content/pdf/10.1007/978-1-4842-3709-0.pdf>
- [7]. Laptick, Sergey. Types of Tracking Systems. How to Monitor Anything from Animals to Construction Equipment. Online. <https://xbsoftware.com/blog/types-of-tracking-system/>